

Diagnostic Accuracy of Glutathione Peroxidase in Serum of Children with Chronic Kidney Disease

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Abstract

Background: Chronic kidney disease (CKD) causes permanent renal function decrease and may lead to ESRD. CKD is a serious public health issue despite medical improvements that have increased survival. Over the past two decades, CKD in children has progressively grown, disproportionately affecting socioeconomically disadvantaged and ethnic minority groups. Overproduction of reactive oxygen species and inadequate antioxidant defenses cause oxidative stress, which causes kidney disorders like CKD. Glutathione peroxidase (GSH-Px) neutralizes oxidative damage. This study aimed to evaluate the diagnostic accuracy of serum GSH-Px levels in differentiating stages of CKD in children. **Methods:** A case–control study was conducted including 120 children who attended Al-Imamin Al-Kadhimein City Hospital. Participants were divided into three groups: 40 children with CKD stages 1–4, 40 children with end-stage CKD, and 40 apparently healthy controls. All children underwent clinical assessment and medical history evaluation. Serum GSH-Px levels were measured using a colorimetric method, and receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve analysis was applied to assess diagnostic performance. **Results:** Serum GSH-Px levels were significantly higher in children with end-stage CKD compared with those with CKD stages 1–4 and healthy controls. GSH-Px demonstrated very good discriminatory power between CKD and healthy children (AUC = 0.823), fair discrimination between end-stage CKD and non-dialysis CKD, and poor discrimination between early-stage CKD and controls. **Conclusions:** Serum GSH-Px may serve as a useful biomarker for differentiating children with CKD from healthy peers, particularly in advanced disease stages, reflecting the role of oxidative stress in CKD progression.

Introduction

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is defined by the presence of structural or functional abnormalities of the kidney, with or without a reduction in glomerular filtration rate (GFR), persisting for at least three months. This concept emphasizes chronicity and kidney damage rather than relying solely on serum creatinine levels. The classification and staging of CKD are primarily based on GFR, which is considered the most reliable indicator of

overall renal function because it incorporates important variables such as age, sex, and body size. Unlike serum creatinine alone, GFR provides a more accurate reflection of kidney function and allows the inclusion of patients with normal or mildly reduced renal function (stages I and II), thereby broadening the clinical applicability of the term CKD [1]. According to the Kidney Disease Outcomes Quality Initiative (KDOQI), CKD is classified into five stages based on GFR

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values. Stages I and II are characterized by preserved or mildly reduced GFR with evidence of kidney damage, commonly persistent albuminuria, whereas stages III and IV represent moderate to severe reductions in GFR. Stage V, also referred to as end-stage renal disease (ESRD), is defined by a GFR below 15 mL/min/1.73 m² or the need for renal replacement therapy. In pediatric practice, estimation of GFR commonly relies on the Schwartz formula, which incorporates serum creatinine, body height, and an age- and sex-specific proportionality constant, making it practical and widely accepted for children [1,2]. Oxidative stress has been increasingly recognized as a key contributor to the initiation and progression of CKD. An imbalance between the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and antioxidant defense mechanisms leads to cellular injury, inflammation, and fibrosis within the kidney. Among antioxidant enzymes, glutathione peroxidase (GPx) plays a central role in detoxifying hydrogen peroxide and lipid peroxides by utilizing reduced glutathione (GSH) as a substrate, thereby limiting oxidative damage. This process depends on selenium as an essential cofactor and operates in close cooperation with catalase and glutathione reductase [2]. Several GPx isoforms are relevant to renal physiology. GPx1 is the predominant intracellular form in the kidney, accounting for the majority of renal GPx activity, and is highly expressed in renal cortical cells, including mitochondria. Experimental studies have shown that GPx1 is involved in protecting renal tissue against oxidative stress, although its precise role in different kidney diseases remains controversial [2,3]. In contrast, GPx3 is an extracellular, plasma-associated enzyme synthesized mainly in the kidney and bound to basement membranes of renal tubular cells. Reduced GPx3 levels in CKD may not only reflect renal injury but also contribute to systemic oxidative stress and remote organ dysfunction, highlighting a potential kidney-organ crosstalk mediated by oxidative pathways [3,4] This study aimed to evaluate the diagnostic accuracy of serum GSH-Px levels in differentiating stages of CKD in children.

Method

This is observational case-control study consisting of 120 children between (2-18) years old of both genders (male and female). samples had been collected from Al-imamin Al-Kadhimeen City Hospital. Inclusion Criteria: About 120 patients / Age of patients between (2 - 18) years / Both genders in Al-Kadhimiya Educational Hospital

Exclusion Criteria:

- 1) The patient that has Renal cancer
- 2) The patient that has antioxidants supplement and vitamins

3) Children with UTI.

Samples were collected from patients and controls by taking five (5) ml of venous blood in plane tube. Blood samples were left to for 30 minutes than centrifuged in 2000 RPM for 15 minutes. A serum is transferred to new tube and kept in -20 C° until assay.

Then the serum will be separated and divided into small amounts in tubes for: The rest will be stored at -20oC until assayed for GSH-Px activity. This will be measured using enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay the activity will be measured using spectrophotometer method. SUNLONGBIOTECH kits (Routine work).

Results

The median PE levels of GSH-Px were significantly higher in the CKD D group than in the CKD NOD and healthy children. However, the median level of blood urea and serum creatinine were significantly higher in the CKD D group. The median levels of all markers in serum were higher in the CKD D group than in the CKD NOD and healthy children group. As in fig 1.

Figure 1: Means of GSH -Px by Group with 95.00% CI Error Bars by the Groups of the Study

In the comparison between CKD and Control groups, the area under the curve (AUC) for GSH Px was 0.823 (95% CI: 0.722 to 0.900), indicating a very good discriminatory power. The optimal cutoff value was determined to be >21.1, with a sensitivity of 75.0% and specificity of 85%. In the comparison between CKD-NoD and Control groups, GSH Px demonstrated an AUC of 0.594 (95% CI: 0.479 to 0.703), indicating poor discriminatory power. The optimal cutoff value was >22.2, with a sensitivity of 57.5% and specificity of 72.50%. In the comparison between CKD and CKD-NoD groups, GSH Px yielded an AUC of 0.659 (95% CI: 0.544 to 0.761), indicating fair discriminatory power. The optimal cutoff value was >20.6, with a sensitivity of 40% and specificity of 95%. As in tables 1 and 2.

Table 1: Comparison between CKD and CKD-NoD Groups

Contrast	Variable	AUC	SE	95% CI	Cutoff	Sens	Spec	+LR	-LR
CKD vs Control	GSH Px	0.823	0.0494	0.722 to 0.900	>21.1	75.00	85.00	5.00	0.29
CKD-NoD vs Control	GSH Px	0.594	0.0669	0.479 to 0.703	>22.2	40.00	95.00	8.00	0.63
CKD vs CKD-NoD	GSH Px	0.659	0.0624	0.544 to 0.761	>20.6	75.0	57.50	1.76	0.43

Note: AUC =Area Under the Curve, SE: stands for Standard Error, 95% CI: Confidence Interval (CI) Cutoff: The cutoff value represents the threshold used to classify individuals into different groups based on the diagnostic test results. It helps determine whether a test result is considered positive or negative, Sens: Sensitivity, Spec: Specificity, +LR: The Positive Likelihood Ratio, -LR: The Negative Likelihood Ratio. The significant p-values GSH-Px indicate that these markers can effectively differentiate between different stage of CKD. The higher levels of GSH-Px in the CKD need dialysis (end stage) group compared to the healthy groups suggest their potential utility as diagnostic marker for distinguishing CKD stages and healthy children cases.

Table 2: Comparison of GSH-Px Parameter Among the Study Groups

Parameter	Subjects	Median	Mean± SD	SEM	p- value	CKD-D	CKD-NoD	Control
GSH-Px Activity	CKD-D	24.20	23.42± 6.78	1.09	< 0.001	A	B	B
	CKD-NoD	18.50	18.81± 8.92	1.43				
	Control	17.10	16.05± 5.18	0.83				

Note: SEM= standard error of the mean, * One way ANOVA test, groups sharing similar letters are statistically not significantly different from each other.

Within the CKD-NoD group, significant correlations were found between Hb g/dl, GSH Px and Hb g/dl and Hb g/dl, Hb g/dl and age, creatinine and urea, DBp and SBp, DBp and weight, DBp and height, DBp and age, SBp and weight, SBp and height, weight and height, weight and age, and height and age. These findings provide

insights into the interrelationships among these parameters and their potential implications for the understanding and management of chronic kidney disease in this specific group. Table presents the results of the correlations. As in table 3.

Table 3: Pearson Correlation Matrix Among GSH Px, Hb g/dl, Creatinine, Urea, DBp, SBp, Weight Kg, Height, and Age within (CKD-NoD) group

Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
GSH Px	.21	-								
Hb g/dl	.38*	.31*	.37*	-						
Creatinine	.03	.12	.03	-.04	-					
Urea	-.10	-.01	-.10	-.23	.78*	-				
DBp	.09	-.02	.03	-.05	.16	.17	-			
SBp	.07	.05	.03	-.13	.27	.21	.49*	-		
Weight	.23	.26	.18	.24	.11	.07	.53*	.54*	-	
Height	.02	.24	-.03	.23	.17	.13	.46*	.48*	.84*	-
Age	.08	.29	.04	.34*	.12	.10	.34*	.43*	.76*	.81*

Within the CKD-D group, significant correlations were found between GSH-Px and creatinine and urea, creatinine and weight, creatinine and height, creatinine and age, urea and weight, urea and height, urea and age, DBp and SBp, weight and height, weight and age,

and height and age. These findings provide insights into the interrelationships among these parameters and their potential implications for the understanding and management of chronic kidney disease in this specific group. As in table 4.

Table 4: Pearson Correlation Matrix Among GSH Px, Hb g/dl, Creatinine, Urea, DBp, SBp, Weight Kg, Height, and Age within (CKD-D) group

Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
GSH Px	-.06	-									
Hb g/dl	-.25	.26	-.29	-							

Creatinine	.08	-.27	.09	.07	-						
Urea	-.01	-.01	.00	.04	.42*	-					
DBp.	.20	-.30	.19	-.13	.16	-.06	-				
SBp.	.25	.07	.26	-.10	.02	-.16	.45*	-			
Weight Kg	.19	.03	.20	.19	.70*	.36*	.10	.06	-		
Height cm	.20	.01	.21	.17	.70*	.33*	.10	.15	.89*	-	
Age	.15	.07	.16	.13	.66*	.39*	.08	.05	.86*	.87*	-
Note. * <i>p</i> < .05.											

Discussion

Glutathione peroxidase activity was significantly higher only in CKD-D versus CKD-NoD, suggesting that other factors affect activity. Glutathione peroxidase is an antioxidant enzyme that may increase in response to oxidative stress [5,6]. Reactive oxygen species (ROS) is an umbrella term that contains oxygen radicals and non-radical compounds such as hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), hydroxyl radicals, lipid radicals, and (phosphorus) lipid hydroperoxides [7]. ROS has long been recognized as a harmful substance, and its excessive accumulation will cause the release of inflammatory factors, enhance the adhesion of inflammatory factors to endothelial cells, and promote apoptosis and even cause cell death. The glutathione peroxidase (GPX) family is one of the main enzymes that protects cells from oxidative stress. In general, GPX exerts the role of oxidative stress by catalyzing the reduction of H₂O₂ and organic hydroperoxides to water and corresponding alcohols, respectively [8]. The study said that increased oxidative stress has been reported in numerous adult studies in patients with CKD. However, there are few reports on the antioxidant system in children with CKD. reported increased lipid peroxidation, monitored by plasma and erythrocyte malondialdehyde (MDA), together with decreased superoxide dismutase, catalase, and glutathione peroxidase activities in children with chronic renal failure before dialysis as compared to healthy age-matched subjects. the loss of antioxidants during dialysis. led to a deficiency of antioxidant enzyme, and it is in disagreement with a present study [9]. Another study has the same view that increasing concentrations of OS markers such as mitochondrial superoxide and oxidized LDL and homocysteine, as well as a deficiency of SOD and GSH, are together with disease progression. The GSH antioxidant system has been reported as one of the first mechanisms to be disturbed in chronic renal failure [10].

Conclusion

Our findings demonstrated that, in the serum of CKD D samples, CKD NOD had significantly greater levels of GSH-Px than healthy children. This implies that they may be useful markers for distinguishing CKD from

healthy, and their application in clinical practice may aid in the selection of individuals who require dialysis or not. Prior to widespread clinical application, multicenter studies with a greater number of cases are required to corroborate our findings.

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